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INTERLAMINAR PROPERTIES OF CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT RESIN FRACTION

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In this work, the influence of resin fraction on the interlaminar properties of continuous glass fiber reinforced PPS (GF/PPS) composites were investigated. The GF/PPS composites were prepared by aqueous suspension prepregging and molding process. The composites were also modified with multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) and silicon carbide (SiC) whiskers in order to enhance the interlaminar properties. Short beam strength (SBS) test and double cantilever beam (DCB) test were adopted to evaluate the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and Mode- I interlaminar fracture toughness respectively.

- **Interlaminar properties of GF/PPS composites with different fiber volume fraction**

The change of interlaminar fracture toughness was attributed to the fiber bridge mechanism. High fiber volume fraction benefit to the formation of fiber bridge and improve the load absorption in crack tip, leading to high fracture toughness.

Fig 1 Fiber volume fraction of SBS samples and DCB samples

Fig 3 ILSS and GIC of GF/PPS composites with different fiber volume fraction

Fig 2 Typical optical image of GF/PPS composites: SBS samples with (a) 20wt% powder contents; (b) 25wt% powder contents; (c) 30wt% powder contents; and DCB samples with (d) 20wt% powder contents; (e) 25wt% powder contents; (f) 30wt% powder contents

Fig 4 SEM images of DCB test fracture surfaces of GF/PPS composites (a) with 61% fiber volume fraction; (b) with 56% fiber volume fraction; (c) with 49% fiber volume fraction

Fig 5 IFSS of GF and PPS modified with MWNTs and SiC whiskers

- **Interface bonding properties of GF and modified PPS**

Compared with that of pristine composites, the IFSS got 43% improvement and 50% improvement at 0.5wt% MWNTs load and 0.5wt% SiC whiskers respectively. However, excessive addition of MWNTs and SiC whiskers caused the decrease of IFSS, which was attributed to the aggregation of particles.

Fig 6 The pull-out morphologies of micro-debonding samples: (a) PPS; (b) with 0.5wt% MWNTs; (c) with 1.0wt% MWNTs; (d) with 1.5wt% MWNTs; (e) with 2.0wt% MWNTs; (f) with 0.5wt% SiC whiskers; (g) with 0.5wt% SiC whiskers; (h) with 0.5wt% SiC whiskers; (i) with 0.5wt% SiC whiskers

- **Interlaminar properties of GF/PPS composites modified with MWNTs and SiC whiskers**

For ILSS, the addition of SiC whiskers got 9.4% improvement compared to unmodified composites. For GIC, the addition of 1wt% MWNTs got 20% improvement in comparison with the pristine composites. The fracture morphologies of modified composites all showed rougher fiber topographies compared with unmodified composites, indicating the increased interface properties.

The distributed MWNTs reduced the stress concentration on interphase and increased the energies consuming when crack propagated.

Fig 9 ILSS and GIC of GF/PPS composites modified with (a) no modifier; (b) 1wt% MWNTs; (c) 1wt% SiC whiskers; (d) 0.5wt% MWNTs and 0.5wt% SiC whiskers

Fig 10 SEM images of DCB test fracture surfaces of GF /PPS composites (a) without modifier;(b) 1wt% MWNTs; (c) 1wt% SiC whiskers, (d) 0.5wt% MWNTs and 0.5wt% SiC whiskers

Fig 11 Illustration of crack propagation in GF /PPS composite modified with MWNTs

THANKS FOR LISTENNING!

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